

Exploiting the design of Surface Plasmon Resonance interfaces for better diagnostics: a perspective review

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Abstract

Surface Plasmon Resonance based-sensors are promising tools for precision diagnostics as they can provide tests useful for early and, whenever possible, non-invasive disease detection and monitoring. The design of novel, robust and effective interfaces enabling the sensing of a variety of molecular interactions in a highly selective and sensitive manner is a necessary step to obtain both accurate and reliable detection by SPR. This review covers the recent research efforts in this area, specifically emphasizing well-designed interfaces and applications in real-life samples. In particular, after a short introduction which identifies some of the critical challenges, the emerging strategies for the integration of the linker, the metal substrate and the recognition element on the sensing interface will be explored and discussed in three sections, as well as the opportunities for building SPR biosensors, easy to use, and with excellent sensitivities. Finally, a summary of some of the more promising and latest diagnostic applications will be provided, presenting a new window into the near-future perspectives.

Keywords: Surface plasmon resonance, biosensors, diagnostics, multiplexing assays, low-fouling surfaces.

1. Introduction

Reliable, rapid, and highly sensitive detection of biomarkers is crucial for appropriate and specific diagnosis and monitoring [1]. Since its first application, many strategies have been optimized to exploit SPR for the sensitive detection of analytes in complex matrices such as biofluids. Continued efforts for nearly 30 years have been made on the development of *i*) universal substrates that allow for the easy assembly of an effective recognition layer aimed at pushing the sensitivity and maximizing selectivity of the SPR sensor [2]; *ii*) new amplification schemes for signal enhancement in ultrasensitive SPR analysis of ultra-low concentrated biomarkers [3]; *iii*) novel strategies of plasmonic signal transduction modes using nanostructures or nanopores for single molecule detection [4]; *iv*) approaches with multiplexing capability to simultaneously reveal, within a single assay, of more than one analyte [5]; *v*) detectors miniaturized to develop portable and affordable SPR systems [6] for the on-site detection [7] and integrated devices for point-of-care (POC) testing [8] also in low-resource settings [9].

Every single component of SPR-based platforms (metal substrate, linker, receptor, transducer, and detector) has been reviewed comprehensively and various SPR applications for clinical, environmental, and food analysis are rapidly progressing [10,11]. Therefore, offering a different point of view, the present review focus on how the design of the SPR interface, referred to as the sensing layer, composed of a metal substrate supporting the SPR phenomenon, a chemical or biological linker, and a surface receptor (in most cases a bioreceptor or recognition element) contributes to improving the overall performance in terms of sensitivity and selectivity of bioassay, by guarantying in the meanwhile, simple assay procedures, and the minimization of fouling phenomenon on plasmonic surface by body fluid sample components.

The ongoing advances of SPR-based platforms aiming to improve the recognition layer's key features could greatly expand the potential of SPR-based sensors in diagnostics. For this reason, such a review focuses explicitly on the appropriate design of the SPR sensing layer. The plethora of options existing for the designed SPR interfaces does not allow a simplified categorization, and for this reason, to

better appreciate the diversity of choices available, the interfaces have been schematically grouped in the following three sections:

- i)* inorganic interfaces when the substrate includes metal films, nanostructures (gold nanoparticles NPs), and periodic nanopatterns;
- ii)* organic interfaces when the linker is composed of thiols, polyethylene glycol (PEG), zwitterionic, bio and/or smart polymers and graphene-coated SPR thin film;
- iii)* biointerfaces when the recognition element consists of several biological entities, such as nucleic acid or analogues, antibodies or aptamers, DNA origami structures and enzymes, independently of chemical linkers or metal substrate used.

The three different components of the SPR sensing layer are frequently used in miscellaneous strategies. The choice of the linker, the metal substrate, and the element recognition is mainly focused on benefits they can bring in terms of the overall SPR sensing performances improvements, with special emphasis on low-fouling activity, sensitivity enhancement (in the pM-fM range or below), multiplexing capability, and real-life sample analysis.

These features are graphically outlined in **Fig. 1**.

Even though the SPR interface shares some features with other plasmonic sensors [12] such as surface-enhanced Raman scattering (SERS) and surface-enhanced fluorescence (SEF), and that SPR detection could be implemented through different couplers such as prisms [13], waveguide [14], grating [15] or fiber coupling [16], the differences between the numerous SPR sensing platforms will not be discussed here. The fundamental theory and comprehensive discussion of the different plasmonic platforms have been extensively discussed in recent reviews [17-19]. Readers are also addressed to published papers describing the future development of SERS [20,21] and SEF [22], such that it will not be a topic of discussion in this perspective.

Instead, this review provides a critical vision of opportunities for developing SPR interfaces, pointing to new directions for the role played by metal substrates, organic linkers, and biorecognition elements for diagnostic applications. In this context, we have mainly reviewed recently presented opportunities

(the last 5 years) in designing SPR sensing interfaces with specific attention to inorganic interfaces allowing the development of multiplexed assays, organic interfaces providing low-fouling sensor surface, and biointerfaces boosting sensitivity and selectivity. The discussed SPR interfaces were classified (Table 1) by evaluating their different nature and the interface's role in maximizing the overall sensing performance. Special attention is devoted to interfaces offering performances good enough to be used with a biofluid.

Fig. 1: Scheme of the different elements of an SPR sensing interface

2. Critical features for SPR interfaces

Various issues have to be addressed in designing a plasmonic interface starting from SPR sensing layer, which comprises different materials, where the surface-immobilized probe or receptor selectively recognizes the target of interest. Traditionally, SPR measurements are performed on thin metal films and excitation produces propagating surface plasmons (SPs) [23], which are charge density oscillations propagating at the metal-dielectric interface. The resulting electromagnetic field is highly sensitive to changes in the refractive index within the surrounding medium [24]. So, an optimal functionalization strategy [25] for the metal surface is strictly required to ensure a cross-talk between the sensing area and the surrounding one at the solid-liquid interface and, subsequently, to obtain a quantifiable SPR signal with an improved signal-to-noise ratio [26].

Moreover, the selection of an appropriate surface immobilization strategy is crucial to bestow the SPR biosensing platform's successful performance, and the choice of the surface receptor [27] for the analysis of complex samples able to satisfy the stringent requirements in diagnostics is always a compromise to be realized between its analytical and functional features.

The adequate metal substrate-receptor thickness with the introduction of a linker [28] provides a sufficient distance from the surface, increasing the accessibility to the recognition element and positively impacting the interaction. It also promotes surface passivation and minimization of fouling at the SPR-active surface [29].

On the other hand, an excessive distance of the recognition element from the functional interface of the SPR biosensor results in a considerable loss in sensitivity since the exponential decay of the evanescent field intensity [30] beyond the metallic surface of the SPR sensor makes layers closer to the gold surface better performing in terms of sensitive detection than further layers. For this reason, antifouling layers with thicknesses ranging from 15 and about 70 nm significantly limit the development of highly sensitive SPR assays for the analysis of clinical samples [31].

However, when adopting longer wavelengths or guided wave SPR [32] and depending on the substrate's geometry, long-range SPRs [33] with deeper penetration depths (200–1400 nm) propagate

along the metal layer. Such configurations are best for sensing targets such as cells [34] and bacteria [35].

Moreover, an SPR architecture bearing a high surface receptor density is certainly beneficial due to the sensor's increased sensitivity, especially for protein quantification assay [36]. Nevertheless, very dense receptor layers with considerable density may cause mass transportation limitation [37], steric hindrance [38], and the risk of data misinterpretation in case of a lack of selectivity [39].

In the case of nucleic acid-based recognition elements, electrostatic repulsions between incoming targets approaching the surface-immobilized probes can become so predominant to prevent a correct interaction in the surface hybridization process [40,41].

Based on the specific application, different surface architecture designs must be considered, as well as the choice of the receptor, which will target the analyte of interest, the appropriate linker, and good surface chemistry for anchoring this receptor to an SPR active layer. Therefore, the selectivity of target recognition, the orientation of the anchored biomolecule acting as the surface receptor, and its surface coverage are the main issues to be tackled to design an effective SPR sensing layer.

After the selection of the recognition element, a critical step in building a new SPR interface is the chemical immobilization strategy applied to bring such elements to the right place with the proper orientation. For the well-established immobilization strategies, we point the reader to the existing literature, where dedicated reviews [42,43] on the importance of surface functionalization strategies are published, discussing costs and benefits, whilst the goal of this review is to emphasize how the different components of the SPR sensing layer, in details the linker, the metal substrate and bioreceptor, can converge to assure the high sensitivity and selectivity for the detection of the target of interest directly in a real sample, and globally, tailoring interface properties for improved SPR biosensing.

3. Inorganic Interfaces

Substrates supporting the SPR phenomenon, from metal films, semiconductors and hybrid metamaterials to various nanostructures, can be exploited to design SPR inorganic interfaces [44,45]. Gold is the most frequently chosen material capable of supporting surface plasmons since it is compatible with straightforward surface chemistries, easily deposited to form a thin film, and resistant to oxidation. Silver and copper are also considered in plasmonic interface design for the inherently higher sensitivities and sharper SPR peak compared to gold. However, their poor chemical stability and tendency to oxidation reduce shelf-life and sensor reproducibility.

Although aluminium has drawn much attention in the past due to its good optical properties, high abundance, low cost, and ease of functionalization [46], the troubles in controlling size and shape during production represent the main detriment of using it. Palladium exhibited excellent sensing properties, but it is too expensive for consideration as a possible layer for commercial devices [47]. Even metal oxides and nitrides have been taken into account as inorganic substrates for SPR sensor design because of their optical properties and biocompatibility; however, they are more challenging to manage through nanofabrication techniques [48,49]. The adoption of other thin metal films such as metal oxide, the effects of indium-molybdenum oxide (IMO), indium tin oxide (ITO) and ZnO on sensitivity, resolution and other properties of sensors have been recently reviewed [50]. Recently, a multi-layer of metal and dielectrics ($\text{SiO}_2/\text{Ag}/\text{SiO}_2$) was used to develop a POC device for stroke biomarkers sensing [51].

Metallic nanostructures whose dimensions are smaller than the wavelength of incident light support the so-called localized surface plasmon resonance (L-SPRs) resulting from the resonant interaction between the light and nanostructure's surface electrons [52]. L-SPR-based sensors are more surface sensitive compared to propagating SPR with the decay length of the electromagnetic field of 10–30 nm [53], compared to 100–400 nm of conventional SPR [54].

The different decay length directly affects the design of the sensing interface, which is particularly challenging when the metallic nanostructures are patterned on substrates. Ideally, all functional

components of the sensing interface should be confined to the nanostructure, and the entire sensing process should be established within a distance from the metallic surface shorter than the decay length. These requirements make the functionalization process and overall interface design more demanding compared to propagating SPR sensors and also highlight the different requirements in terms of materials used for the fabrication of the sensor interface [55,56], and methods adopted for the site-specific functionalization [57].

Nanomodified structures such as nanohole [58], nanoslit [59], nanorings in the *array* format [60], metal nanoparticles and randomly distributed nanostructures have been investigated for high-throughput and high-sensitivity SPR sensing applications [61]. Other remarkable nanostructures such as nanocrescents [62], nanocross [63] and nanobowls [64] have been summarized by Jiang et al [65]. All over, these nanostructures that share scattering and strong absorption from incident light, trigger a localized SPR phenomenon and a consequent enhancement of the local electromagnetic field, in the form of a *hot spot*. They can be described as intrinsically miniaturized versions of SPR sensors without requiring a sophisticated optical system. Besides, the size of the nanostructure confines the sensing area to the nanostructure, expanding the throughput and offering unparalleled capabilities for multiplexed assay. Hence, L-SPR enables high-throughput detection for simultaneous recognition of different concentrations of target biomarkers.

Even though other plasmonic nanoparticles are accessible, gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) are positioned at the forefront of the SPR enhancement strategy, presumably due to their easy synthesis and simple conjugation using established protocols [66].

Both uniformly distributed NPs and periodic nanopatterns arranged on flat SPR substrates produce higher reproducibility and allow for multiplexing. Most flat substrates employ glass on which to deposit AuNPs and AuNPs can form multiple layers on this surface by successively binding to other different-sized NPs, enhancing sensitivity. For instance, a hetero-assembled sandwich structure-based L-SPR sensor [67] has been realized to reveal hepatitis B surface antigen (HBsAg) at 100 fg mL^{-1} within 10–15 min. The L-SPR platform consists of an AuNPs sandwich-immunoassay in which,

firstly, a substrate was prepared by depositing anti-HBsAg on glass and then exposing it to HBsAg. Then, a second layer of anti-HBsAg-conjugated AuNPs was added, thus forming the hetero-assembled sandwich structure. This bilayer afforded enhanced LSPR signals, and smaller AuNPs made stronger L-SPR signals, resulting in more *hot spots*. Their results were validated in spiked human serum samples, showing high selectivity against other antigens such as α fetoprotein (AFP), C-reactive protein (CRP), and prostate-specific antigen (PSA).

With the same underlying principle, the deposition on substrates of NPs with different dimensions and shapes exhibiting different optical properties may be used for detecting multiple analytes. This advantage was proved by Kim et al. [68] by developing a ‘shape-code’ biosensor for simultaneous detection of τ (tau) protein, Amyloid-beta ($A\beta$) 1–40, and $A\beta$ 1–42 biomarkers, without further procedures for separation from multiple samples. A differently shaped (or sized) Au nanoparticle, in detail, AuNPs (50 nm diameter), short NRs (1.6 aspect ratio), and long NRs (3.6 aspect ratio) was assigned and conjugated with the corresponding antibody. The described “shape-code” LSPR-based sensing platform surpasses the minimum clinically relevant sensitivities for each AD biomarker by giving LOD for $A\beta$ 1–40, $A\beta$ 1–42, and τ protein equal to 34.9 fM, 26 fM, and 23.6 fM, respectively, using the spiked plasma samples. (**Fig. 2A**). Microfluidics can be exploited for optimal fluid management combined with plasmonic nanoapertures as nanochannels, advantageously employed for capturing pathogens specifically around the detection *hot spots* [69]. Soler et al. [70] adopted a similar strategy to simultaneously and rapidly detect two common bacteria causing sexually transmitted infections (*Chlamydia trachomatis* and *Neisseria gonorrhoeae*), without cell lysis or DNA extraction, directly in urine samples at levels as low as 300 and 1500 CFU mL⁻¹, respectively. The platform employs spectral SPR imaging and gold nanohole arrays that use extraordinary optical transmission (EOT) fabricated on silicon nitride substrates and selectively functionalized with specific antibodies captured on the surface of nanoholes via protein A/G. (**Fig. 2B**).

Fig. 2: A) Schematic illustration of shape-code plasmonic biosensor for multiple Alzheimer's disease biomarkers. Reprinted with permission from Ref. [68]; B) Plasmonic elements combined with capture antibodies to detect unlabeled intact bacteria selectively. Reprinted with permission from Ref. [70].

The authors showed that bacteria are detected and quantified in a single assay by discriminating both types of bacteria mixed in the same liquid sample. The device is miniaturized, thus illustrating a step towards a rapid, POC diagnostic test.

A recent report described an L-SPR sensing chip [71] containing a gold nanorod array functionalized with capture antibodies, microfluidic channels, and micromechanical valves for multiplexed detection of four representative cancer biomarkers CEA, CA125, CA-15-3, and ErbB2 in human serum. The microfluidic LSPR sensor was tested simultaneously with the four antigens displaying minimum cross-reactivity. With precise fluid control, it could achieve automatic, quantitative, and multiplexed cytokine detection in human serum with extremely low LODs (0.21 U mL^{-1} for CA15-3, 0.139 U mL^{-1} for CA 125, 1.021 U mL^{-1} for CEA, and 3.9 ng mL^{-1} for HER2).

As an example of various strategies [72], a highly sensitive SPR biosensor was assembled on graphene oxide-gold nanoparticles (GO-AuNPs) composites, which could amplify the signal generated by plasmon material and boost the sensitivity of detection up to femto (fM) to atto molar (aM) level to perform the detection of miRNA and small molecule adenosine [73]. Dual amplification was obtained by the generation of two layers of GO-AuNPs composite. The bottom layer on the sensor chip provided a surface for immobilizing thiolated DNA bound to the GO-AuNPs, acting as both a capture

and recognition element. The upper layer served as a signal-amplification element when the target miRNA was hybridized to miRNA-141, and the DNA-GO-AuNPs complex was produced on the surface of the SPR chip. (**Fig. 3**) The two-layer nature of this strategy improved LOD as low as 0.1 fM, compared with the previous study using the single layer used as a substrate [74], achieving sensitive and rapid (~ 60 min) detection of miRNA-141 extracted from different cancer cell lines. In addition, miRNA-141 was successfully revealed against other members belonging to the miRNA-200 family, also in diluted human serum with excellent selectivity. Most importantly, small molecules like adenosine could also be detected using this sensing approach with a LOD of 0.1 pM, enabling a promising chemical and biosensing application.

Fig. 3: Schematic illustration of the SPR biosensor based on the GO-AuNPs composites. Reprinted with permission from Ref. [74].

The use of optical fiber with its many physical modifications represents an outstanding scaffold for localized SPR substrate in biosensing and bioanalysis, with a multitude of benefits such as resistance to interference, ease of use, low cost, flexibility and possibility for miniaturization [75,76]. Many fiber optic-SPR (FO-SPR) platforms [77,78] have been reported for multifunctional detection of

analytes in complex matrices such as human serum [79-81], plasma [82-84], and whole blood [81,85]. Most importantly, a lot of changes concerning FO geometry or configuration, such as the use of cascaded fibers [86], multi-core fibers [87] or holey fibers [88] that can enable multiplexed detection, have been adopted. Lu et al. [85] described a fast and sensitive FO-SPR based immunoassay for detecting therapeutic monoclonal antibody infliximab (IFX) in treated patients suffering from inflammatory bowel disorders (IBD). The binding between IFX-conjugated gold nanoparticles deposited on an optical fiber and IFX induced a shift in SPR spectra. The target was detected in just 10 min with LOD of 1.42, 1.00, and 1.34 ng mL⁻¹, respectively, for 100-fold diluted serum, plasma and whole blood. The sensor performance was validated using clinical samples from IBD patients such as dried blood spots, with LOD below 2 ng mL⁻¹ and optimized to build calibration curves useful in POC applications. (Fig. 4)

Fig. 4: Schematic illustration of FO-SPR biosensor used for determining IFX concentrations in a variety of matrices. Reprinted with permission from Ref. [85].

To some extent, SPR interfaces based on inorganic substrates such as metal films, nanostructures (e.g AuNPs), FO-SPR and periodic nanopatterns have addressed many challenges, and extensive efforts have been made at developing SPR interfaces with integrated microfluidics allowing high-throughput and multiplex sensing. However, despite their attractiveness, efforts still need to be made to overcome

other issues, including developing strategies for the large-scale fabrication of nanostructures for suitable patterned interfaces.

4. Organic Interfaces

Since SPR needs a metallic surface, most often gold, a well-established functionalization strategy takes advantage of a highly ordered self-assembled monolayer (SAM) (e.g., alkanethiols) in which the direct bond between the thiol moiety occurs over the gold surface. With this layer, antibodies are still the most selected receptors for SPR assays. The method of the immobilization of the antibody, as the recognition element, over this organic layer should provide a robust and covalent immobilization of the antibody, preserving both its native form and the appropriate orientation and exposure of the binding sites.

Oriented immobilization through affinity interactions, achieved using recombinant/tagged receptors or A, or G proteins [89], allowed for the enhancing capability, minimizing steric hindrance, non-specific binding and antibody inactivation.

The latest trends in SAM-based-immobilization methods employ oligo- or polyethylene glycols (OEG or PEG) as spacers to enhance assay sensitivity. The most frequently used are organic linkers with a long aliphatic chain (e.g. mercaptoundecanoic acid (MUA) or mercaptohexadecanoic acid (MHDA)), capable of constructing a pattern of assemblies consisting of a spacer molecule exhibiting passivating properties and, a functional group (generally, a COOH terminal) that via EDC/NHS coupling chemistry, attach the antibody through primary amine groups on its surface. Nevertheless, these functional linkers are not strictly limited to the anchoring of antibodies, but they can be used in the presence of any capture moiety bearing a reactive group against the SAM terminal [90].

In 2021, Ribeiro et al. [91] reported an SPR methodology with an electrochemical readout for the label-free and sensitive detection of breast cancer biomarker CA 15-3 in human serum samples. Ultrathin films (with an overall thickness of 1.4 ± 0.4 nm after antibody immobilization) were

arranged from short-chain carboxyl acid-terminated SAM of mercaptosuccinic acid (MSA), instead of frequently used 11-MUA to optimize both electron transfer and surface plasmon processes, avoiding surface blocking to the electron transfer process. In addition, the experimental protocol was rigorously optimized and implemented to reduce matrix effects on the sensor surface for enhanced detection of the circulating protein biomarker in human serum samples, allowing the application of the eSPR biosensor in a clinical setting.

Later, the same research group described the ultrasensitive screening of miRNA-145 by an innovative electrochemistry-assisted SPR approach [92]. Thiolated RNA probes were covalently immobilized on gold sensor surface, using this time, the co-immobilization of hydrophilic 2-mercaptoethanol (ME) as a lateral spacer to reduce steric hindrance. The real-time SPR monitoring of the hybridization event between RNA fragments and complementary immobilized probes is followed by the potential-assisted deposition of a redox probe on the SPR sensor surface resulting in a much larger SPR response because of the electrochemical process. The developed eSPR biosensor with a limit of detection (LOD) of 0.56 fM was successfully used to reveal miRNA-145 in human serum, showing in the meanwhile high selectivity against single-base and two-base mismatch sequences.

Apart from alkanethiols favorably used for many applications [93], other useful linkers are being investigated that consist of dopamine [94], polymers, polypeptides [95,96] and polyelectrolytes [97] that emerged in the literature with great potential as antifouling coatings for biosensing in biomedical applications. For instance, Dang et al. [98] improved the fouling performance by grafting a phosphocholine copolymer to the polydopamine surface, significantly minimizing the amount of non-specific binding from various biomolecules (platelet, fibroblast, bacteria cells, BSA and plasma fibrinogen). Likewise, He and co-workers [99] designed a composite layer with enhanced antifouling performance through the coupling of dopamine to hyaluronic acid before the gold surface attachment, finally providing a common approach to surface modification to design SPR interfaces with ultralow protein adsorption.

A new dual-functional low-fouling poly-L-lysine (PLL)-based polymer with nanoparticle-enhanced surface plasmon resonance biosensing for the detection of circulating tumor DNA (ctDNA) point mutation directly in human plasma has been presented [100]. The PLL-based polymer contains densely immobilized anionic oligopeptide side-chains to create a charge-balanced layer for non-specific adsorption of undesired biomolecules coming from the biofluid. At the same time, sparsely attached peptide nucleic acid (PNA) probes capture complementary KRAS mutated circulating DNA sequences from colorectal cancer patients at attomolar level (2.5 aM) with optimal resistance to fouling effect.

SPR organic interfaces can also be fabricated by self-assembly of antifouling zwitterionic materials (such as carboxybetaine (CB), sulfobetaine (SB) and phosphorylcholine (PC)) [96]. Although these coatings showed, after exposure to both individual proteins and complex media, a more remarkable ability to resist protein adsorption than conventional SAMs and PEG-based layers, the preservation of their antifouling characteristics while introducing functionalization to immobilize bioreceptors for biosensing is still a challenge [101]. In this direction, Homola et al. [102] conducted an extensive study of several carboxyl-functionalized coatings, exploiting the influence of functionalization on the antifouling activity, where activation of the functional groups of specific zwitterionic brushes useful to the conjugation severely reduces their antifouling properties. More recently, a triethylene glycol (PEG (3))-pentamer carboxybetaine (PPCB) linker has been proposed [31] to assemble a new SPR interface displaying a thickness of less than 2 nm and outstanding antifouling activity to both undiluted and diluted human plasma samples, also achieving the relevance for the SPR biosensing of human arginase 1 in plasma, a biomarker over-expressed in cancer patients.

In designing an SPR interface, biomimetic linkers can be considered by taking inspiration from nature with the great advantage that the recognition event can be likely monitored on a platform more representative of a physiological environment. Biomimetic interfaces based on lipid bilayers have also been implemented as simplified models of the cellular membrane, whose components can be modified to allow specific SPR-based assays to be conducted at the lipid membrane interface.

A recent report [103] combines an oriented antibody layer immobilized onto a gold chip modified with a mixed SAM of 3-mercapto-1-propanol (MPO) and thiolated protein A and further post-immobilization surface passivation employing a positively charged lipid bilayer mimic, 2-dioleoyl-sn-glycero-3-ethylphosphocholine (EPC+), with improved resistance to the adsorption of components of undiluted human plasma (**Fig. 5A**) compared to the natural, zwitterionic, 1-palmitoyl-2-oleoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphocholine (POPC) membrane. The devised layer was successfully applied to support the detection of IgG in undiluted serum and cholera toxin in plasma samples. The addition of graphene and its derivatives [104] as thin films coated onto the SPR sensor proved the importance of graphene as the sensing element triggering a significant field enhancement at the substrate interface, concerning those with bare gold thin films [105].

Integrated with other composite materials, graphene oxide (GO) is a model of how the interface design must consider both biomolecule immobilization strategy and analysis in complex matrices due to the high degree of non-specific adsorption for this surface. Nevertheless, while it allows for sensitive detection of various biomarkers [106], multiple and time-consuming labor steps are necessary for its synthesis, reducing efficiency in interface design and development.

Fig. 5: **A)** Schematic representation of a sensory interface for IgG detection in undiluted serum based on a positively charged lipid bilayer coating. Reprinted with permission from Ref. [103]; **B)** Schematic illustration for the immobilization of the biomarker anti-cytokeratin-19 (anti-CK19) antibody on the GO-COOH-based SPR chip using an immunoassay to detect lung cancer antigen and calibration curves for the detection of different concentrations of CK19 protein in PBS buffer and spiked 10% human plasma. Reprinted with permission from Ref. [107].

Chiu et al. [107] demonstrated a carboxyl-functionalized GO (GO-COOH)-coated SPR immunosensor for detecting cytokeratin 19 (CK19), a biomarker of non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC), in spiked human plasma samples. By using cystamine as a linker on the GO-COOH, an extremely low amount of CK19-specific antibody was immobilized on the sensing layer, and the kinetic analysis revealed a shorter response time with a better sensitivity in a highly diluted sample (0.001–100 pg mL⁻¹, LOD of ~0.05 pg mL⁻¹ for CK19 protein in human plasma) than conventional SPR biosensors (**Fig. 5B**). The reported sensor showed high specificity and stability. Hence, detecting the biomarkers in clinical samples can be potentially performed with excellent accuracy for diagnosing numerous other diseases.

With an approach different from He et al. [108], the specific sensing of folic acid proteins directly in human serum was achieved via the buildup of π interaction on the graphene-coated SPR chip and the folic acid receptors. Graphene was integrated as part of the surface-passivation procedure to develop an SPR gold surface capable of blocking non-specific interactions on the SPR chip, by mixing human serum with BSA. The assembled chip has excellent reproducibility, with a linear range collected up to a concentration of 500 fM and a prolonged lifetime. To accomplish wider dynamic ranges and relevant sensitivity levels (LODs in the low fM concentrations), graphene and its derivatives were used in some late plasmonic strategies by benefiting from the unique properties of gold and silver nanoparticles [109,110] integrated into inorganic interfaces.

Organic linkers are frequently used to design of SPR interfaces minimizing the non-specific adsorption of components from complex matrices in which biomarkers are present at low concentrations (often below pg mL⁻¹) [111]. Approaches for the fabrication of such interfaces that exploit SAM of thiols, PEG, zwitterionic polymers, or other coatings, such as bioinspired polymers,

should be compatible with the small-scale sensing region of SPR sensors. Additional challenges to integrating the most advanced interfaces into devices for in-vitro diagnostics are device miniaturization capacity and cost-effectiveness production of the functional interfaces.

5. Biointerfaces

This section focuses on the recognition element intended as an affinity or catalytic component of the SPR interface, immobilized on the SPR active surface and able to interact with clinically relevant biomarkers in body fluids. As stated before, it helps to improve overall SPR performance, particularly in achieving selectivity and ultrasensitivity in the assay.

Antibodies are widely used affinity bioreceptors capable of recognizing a target molecule selectively. Y-shaped immunoglobulin G (IgG) is the most commonly encountered antibody in biosensing [112]. It is composed of one heavy chain (Fc) and two domains bearing the binding site (Fab), and at least one of the antigen-binding sites must be accessible and exposed [113]. Unfortunately, the environment and how they are immobilized on the sensor surface may alter their conformation and biological activity, resulting in poor sensing performances [114]. Therefore, the recognition process can be improved by controlling the orientation and surface density of the surface-immobilized antibody [115]. A high surface coverage with a randomly oriented layer can be obtained through surface physisorption [116] or tethering [117,118]. An oriented immobilization through covalent chemisorption, protein G or fragmented antibodies has been instead demonstrated to improve the sensing performances in terms of sensitivity and dynamic range [119-121]. Harpaz and co-workers [122] used a specific antibody covalently coupled to the surface for sensing stroke biomarkers, with a sensitivity and specificity better than 85% and clinically relevant LOD. Also, the use of synthetic receptors, such as molecularly imprinted polymers (MIPs) [123] has been shown to minimize diffusion distances of the target to the binding sites, as well as improve steric hindrance [124-125].

The success of antibodies as affinity recognition elements has motivated research in the field of aptamers in different applications of analytical detection, spanning from molecular diagnosis [126,127] to environmental monitoring and food safety [128]. Aptamers are DNA or RNA sequences folding into well-defined and stable 3D configurations. They interact with target molecules with good affinity and selectivity [129] and simplify storage requirements providing robust and cost-effective SPR sensing platforms.

Wu et al. [130] described an AuNP-enhanced SPR detection of C-reactive protein (CRP) using an aptamer–antibody sandwich assay. A CRP specific aptamer was immobilized on the SPR active gold surface, taking advantage of the simple immobilization chemistry afforded by thiolated DNA. SPR signals referring to CRP binding were compared to those of a direct antibody enhancement and a conjugated antibody–gold nanoparticle enhancement. The AuNP-enhanced aptamer–antibody sandwich assay provided the best results with the lowest detection limit and was used to detect CRP concentrations ranging from 10 pM to 100 nM in diluted human serum. Besides sensitivity, the selectivity of this aptamer-based SPR biosensor was also demonstrated with five interferent proteins (human immunoglobulin G, (IgG), human serum albumin (HSA), haemoglobin (Hb), transferrin (TRF) and myoglobin (Myo)). **(Fig. 6A)**

Loyez et al. [131] demonstrated the rapid detection of circulating breast cancer cells, using HER2 protein biomarkers at low concentrations, employing an FO sensor and an aptamer-based sensing strategy. A selected DNA aptamer against mammaglobin-A (MAMA2), a protein present at the surface of circulating human breast cancer cells, was immobilized on the fiber surface (a tilted fiber Bragg gratings into a single-mode silica FO with a deposited ~50 nm gold film on both sides) to detect tumor cells expressing MAMA2 protein with a LOD of 49 cells mL⁻¹. AuNP-enhanced detection improved the effectiveness of the aptasensor by two orders of magnitude by detecting a lower cancer cells concentration (10 cells mL⁻¹) with good specificity as compared to control cell line such as HEK cells not expressing MAMA proteins.

Fig. 6: A) Schematic illustration of the AuNP enhanced SPR biosensor with an aptamer-antibody sandwich assay. SPR response ($\Delta\theta$) vs CRP concentrations is also shown for (a) the aptamer direct adsorption, (b) aptamer-antibody sandwich assay, (c) AuNP enhanced aptamer-antibody sandwich measurements. Reprinted with permission from Ref. [130]. B) Schematic illustration of the fabricated AIV detection biosensor based on 3 way-Junction DNA (3 WJ DNA) structure and hollow Au spike-like nanoparticles. Reprinted with permission from Ref. [136]. C) Schematic representation of the multiplex miRNA SPRi biosensor based on strand displacement amplification (SDA) and AuNP signal enhancement. Reprinted with permission [145].

To further highlight the remarkable properties of the aptamer-based affinity interface, an aptasensor [132] detecting label-free thrombin (Th) in 10% human plasma samples with no need for signal amplification was fabricated using polymeric brushes (poly(HPMA-co-CBMAA)) to minimize nonspecific adsorption of not-target and interfering components and prevent coagulation processes on the sensor surface. Such a biosensor has been proposed as the first step toward developing a sensitive POC device for the aptamer-based detection of Th in human blood.

Two different 3D DNA origami structures were assembled starting from a 24-helix bundle-shaped origami and designed with a DNA tetrahedron to arrange with nanoscale precision and both parallel or perpendicular orientation Th-specific aptamers with tuned density and distance from the FO-SPR surface. The platform detected Th with a wide linear range (1–248 nM) [133] and LOD within the physiological levels in blood clot events, even if the applicability in the clinical sample has not yet been investigated.

DNA scaffolds and origami-shaped structures [134] can conveniently be employed in designing and implementing biointerfaces, widening opportunities for immobilizing various structural probes (such as DNA tetrahedron) [135] on the surface of the SPR platform. Moreover, compared to ssDNA or dsDNA bearing only two termini, each arm of the DNA origami, such as 3 Way Junction DNA, can significantly advance the range of detection capabilities and act as a multifunctional receptor.

To simplify the fabrication process on a single and label-free platform, a multifunctional DNA as a recognition element consisting of a 3 way-Junction DNA (3 WJ DNA) structure was proposed to integrate target recognition by an aptamer probe, signal enhancement, and immobilization onto the sensor surface [136]. Each part of DNA 3WJ has been tailored to a hemagglutinin (HA) binding aptamer, fluorescein (FAM) dye, and thiol moiety. The authors introduced 3 WJ DNA on the surface of hollow Au spike-like nanoparticles immobilized onto an indium-tin-oxide (ITO) substrate and used for the localized-SPR sensing. (**Fig. 6B**) The device performances were evaluated against clinical

samples by also testing the assay selectivity with related and non-related proteins. The device could detect the avian influenza virus (AIV H5N1) in serum with 1 pM LOD.

A potentially limiting factor is represented by the high level of divalent metal ions (10-20 mM Mg²⁺) required to preserve DNA origami nanostructure. Such a constraint may limit the use of DNA origami nanostructure, especially considering that cells do not resist these extreme conditions [137]. In addition, since nucleic acid biomarkers such as microRNA, cell free-DNAs, and circulating tumor DNAs are available at extremely low concentrations [138], enzymatic amplification strategies are often required to detect them at clinically significant expression levels [137].

Enzymes, such as polymerase, nicking endonuclease, exonuclease, and ligase, represent model systems of catalytic elements. The specific recognition between a target (typically DNA or RNA) and these bioreceptors, enhances biosensor sensitivity [139] by triggering enzymatic reactions (e.g., rolling circle amplification (RCA) [140], strand-displacement amplification (SDA) [141], and hybridization chain reaction (HCR)) [142] that increase the concentration of the target sequence.

Unlike PCR amplification-based strategies involving time and labor-consuming steps, SPR assays integrating DNA-modifying enzymes can be performed under isothermal conditions. Such isothermal amplification assays [143,144] overcome some of the limitations of PCR-based methods, not involving complex sample processing protocols, allowing faster reactions and minimizing risks for sample contaminations.

Wei et al. [145] developed an SPRI biosensor that integrated strand displacement amplification (SDA) with AuNPs to simultaneously detect miR-21 and miR-192 at the low picomolar range in diluted serum. A thiolated DNA capture probe was immobilized on the sensor surface. In the presence of target, the miRNAs can hybridized specifically with their recognition sequence in each amplification probe of the hairpin that contain also a common domain, producing the opening of the hairpin probe loop and the starting of the SDA cycle. Finally, the released targets hybridized with the captured probes on the sensor surface and the DNA functionalized AuNPs, resulting in strong amplified SPR signals detected simultaneously in dual channels of the SPR Imaging sensor (**Fig. 6C**).

Ki et al. [146] employed a localized SPR biosensor to identify miR-10b, a gastric cancer biomarker, sequentially using a duplex-specific nuclease (DSN) and a hybridization chain reaction (HCR). The approach involves an enzyme-supported target recycling when the target miRNA hybridizes the DNA probe immobilized onto a gold surface. DSN can only digest DNA strand of the DNA:RNA duplex, so miRNA dissociates from the duplex and participate in another hybridization event. The following step implies creating a DNA sandwich formed by the ssDNA sequence of the capture probe that acts as the initiator and binding the helper probe. The released miRNA is then quantified using a sequence-specific HCR and tannic acid-functionalized DNA-AuNPs. Tannic acid is a gallol-rich polyphenolic compound able to bind the phosphate backbone of DNA via hydrogen bonding. By monitoring L-SPR adsorption signal a 2.45 pM LOD, both in vitro, plasma and urine samples from a xenograft mouse model was calculated with a linear range between 5 pM and 10 nM.

Amplification strategies often require pre-analytical sample treatments. More, factors such as the microsystem environment, reaction conditions, reagents instability and storage may affect the enzymatic activity, thus reducing the efficiency of the enzymatic interface.

Other biointerfaces benefits from using DNA analogues such as locked nucleic acid (LNA) [147] or peptide nucleic acid (PNA) [148] to increase the sensitivity and selectivity of the probe-target recognition process [149]. PNA is a synthetic DNA analogue with a polyamide chain instead of the negatively charged sugar-phosphate backbone. This unique structural feature allows PNA to base-pair with nucleic acids with high affinity, selectivity and stability. At low ionic strength, PNA probes can hybridize complementary sequences at temperatures that do not allow DNA hybridization. Such a peculiar property is valuable when interfering RNA or DNA molecules exist in the sample, or nucleic acid involves secondary structures to a greater extent.

Calcagno et al. [150] used an SPR Imaging setup to detect a Y-chromosome specific sequence (sex-determining region Y, SRY) from cell-free fetal DNA circulating in maternal plasma. A SRY PNA probe was immobilized onto the gold surface and biotinylated oligonucleotides were immobilized onto functionalized AuNPs to bind male DNA and enhance the detected SPR signal. The proposed

SPR assay allowed the detection of male DNA in 2.5 aM mixtures of male and female genomic DNAs. Since no amplification of the DNA sequence was required, the risk of sample contamination is minimized, thus establishing a straightforward pre-analytical protocol skipping costly, time-consuming, and prone to errors PCR-based procedures.

Nanoparticle-enhanced SPR imaging biosensors have been exploited to detect single point mutations in non-amplified human genomic DNA with attomolar LOD and RAS mutated DNAs circulating in the plasma of colon cancer patients, demonstrating the potential for analyzing liquid biopsy samples [151].

SPR biointerfaces discussed in this section rely on affinity or catalytic interactions and show excellent ultrasensitivity, selectivity, repeatability and low cross-reactivity in real-life samples analysis. In particular, they provide remarkable performances in terms of LOD, accuracy and quantification capacity when coupled with modified nanomaterials. Such performances make them next-generation interfaces for detecting rare analytes in biological and bodily fluids. Nevertheless, their integration into sensing devices compatible with low-resource settings' operational capacity is still challenging. Across these three sections, we have discussed the growing trend to utilize SPR sensing interfaces for advanced measurement capabilities, including multiplexed sensing and ultrasensitive analysis while keeping the ability to detect disease indicator biomarkers with high selectivity and to identify minute amounts of them directly in complex clinical samples. A list of the SPR interfaces with application in real-world samples discussed in this review and their performances is provided in **Table 1**.

6. Conclusion and future perspectives

High healthcare management standards, necessary to provide better diagnostics, could be achieved by making an early and non-invasive diagnosis with POC devices based on SPR sensing.

The success and attractiveness of SPR sensing in diagnostics are motivated by the benefits of the discussed biosensing interfaces. These include identifying the target in the presence of many interfering components, typically available in clinical samples such as serum and plasma. In this case, specific linkers (thiols, PEG, zwitterionic, or other smart coatings) play a crucial role in minimizing the fouling of unspecific components on the sensing surface. Such a feature positively impacts on sensor selectivity, reuse, stability, and reproducibility and enables the detection of clinically relevant biomarkers. Other linkers, such as bioinspired polymers and polymers aiming at simulating the cell membrane, are constantly investigated to help achieve the above-mentioned objectives.

The variability of real-world matrices restricts the adoption of universal antifouling linkers, thus making the majority of SPR diagnostic applications depending on the properties of each biofluid. Clinical specimens such as urine, saliva, sweat, and breath provide excellent non-invasive body fluid collection opportunities. From this perspective, improving the analytical performance by adopting graphene or graphene oxide (GO) as a functional linker between the metal film and the bioreceptor has the strong potential to increase the sensitivity in the identification of ultra-low concentrated biomarkers.

The capacity of some nanometric structures to strongly confine electromagnetic radiations is the key to reaching multiplex and high-throughput capabilities in SPR analysis. Differently shaped NPs or 2D materials combined with optical fiber-based SPR sensors, enabling optical spectroscopy to be performed on areas poorly accessible to conventional spectroscopy, over large distances, may allow the development of devices for challenging applications in clinical diagnostics and several portable sensors have been already successfully developed to detect low concentrations of biomarkers with performances comparable to conventional laboratory testing.

The integration of microfluidic devices with SPR sensing delineates a strategy to overcome several hurdles as it gives the SPR sensor the potential to combine attomolar sensitivity with minimal sample volume requirements. The input of microfluidics assures a high-precision handling of liquid samples while the incorporation of NPs and nanoarray into the microfluidics integrates optical features for

sensors based L-SPR. Such a combination, may also help mimicking the extra and intracellular environment, emphasizing the importance of a well-designed SPR interface to open new avenues for in vivo applications requesting the detection of cells, exosomes, virus or bacteria.

Considerable interest in adopting technologies relying on SPR and nanomaterials is being demonstrated at the industrial level, and we do believe it will consolidate during the next decade.

SPR biointerfaces provide a versatile platform to selectively capture rare biological targets through affinity bioreceptors such as aptamers, DNA origami, or DNA analogues such as PNA probes and/or facilitate the detection and quantification process even through catalytic bioreceptors as enzymes.

Such biointerfaces are created by developing strategies to integrate the different SPR sensing elements to guarantee sensor selectivity and sensitivity while reducing cross-reactivity and eliminating false positive outcomes.

Biosensors are often expected to operate with LOD values lower than the physiological concentration of most biomarkers available in bodily fluids to support their relevance and validation for in vivo biosensing. An essential feature of future methods for SPR biomarker monitoring will be represented by multifunctional interfaces that can simultaneously detect different cancer biomarkers in plasma, serum, and tissues.

Looking toward the future, innovations in nanoscale engineering of SPR interfaces will result in a growing number of SPR assays for diagnostic applications. Suppose this means moving to the next stage of real-world applications. In that case, it will depend on the clinical translation of the SPR interfaces applied in a lab setting to a final sensor format with the demonstration of their applicability as an integrated device, compact, accurate, and reliable, aiming to meet the requirements of improved medical diagnostics.

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Author statement

Roberta D’Agata: Conceptualization, Visualization, Original draft Preparation, Writing – review & editing. **Noemi Bellasai:** Writing – review & editing. **Giuseppe Spoto:** Writing – review & editing. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Table 1: SPR interfaces with application in real-world samples discussed in this review and their performances

SPR INTERFACE CLASSIFICATION	SUBSTRATE	LINKER	RECOGNITION ELEMENT	LINEAR RANGE/LOD	BIOMARKER	CLINICAL SPECIMEN	ASSAY FEATURES AND CAPABILITIES FOR DIAGNOSIS	REF.
INORGANIC	glass substrate fabricated with heteroassembled AuNPs sandwich assay	0.5 % APTES solution	anti-HBsAg antibody	100 fg mL ⁻¹ – 1 µg mL ⁻¹ / 100 fg mL ⁻¹	hepatitis B surface antigen (HBsAg)	human serum	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> high selectivity tested against other antigens (AFP, CRP,PSA) and mixtures of these antigens <ul style="list-style-type: none"> assay time ~ 10–15 min 	[67]
	50 nm gold nanospheres (AuNSs), aspect ratio 1.6 gold nanorods (A.R. 1.6 AuNRs) and A.R. 3.6 AuNRs	heterobifunctional COOH-PEG-SH	antibody	4.9 fM 26 fM 23.6 fM	amyloid beta (Aβ) 1–40, β 1–4, τ protein	blood	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> the colorimetric feature enables multiplex biomarker detection from a single sample no additional steps for protein identification 	[68]
	nanohole arrays fabricated on free-standing silicon nitride membranes	PEGylated SAM	the recombinant protein A/G	300 CFU mL ⁻¹ 1500 CFU mL ⁻¹	Chlamydia trachomatis Neisseria gonorrhoeae bacteria	urine	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> microfluidic multiplexed detection of whole-cell bacteria in urine samples no sample pretreatment or amplification 	[70]
	gold nanorod arrays on glass	SAM of mercaptoundecanoic acid (MUA)	capture antibody (cAb)	4.2–75.4 U mL ⁻¹ / 1.85 U mL ⁻¹ / 2.575–6.089 kU mL ⁻¹ / 1.021 kU mL ⁻¹ / 166.7–2422.3 ng mL ⁻¹ / 76.19 ng mL ⁻¹ / 80.5–1904.8 ng mL ⁻¹ / 31.9 ng mL ⁻¹	CA15-3 CA125 CEA ErbB2	human serum	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> quantitative multiplexed detection of four breast cancer markers through orthogonally crossing channels compartmented by micromechanical valves 	[71]

	two layers of GO-AuNPs	thiocyanuric acid	thiolated capture DNA or split aptamer	141 fM 0.1 pM	miRNA-141 adenosine molecule	prostate carcinoma cell lines (22Rv1), hepatocellular carcinoma cell lines (SMMC-7721), colon cancer cell lines (LoVo) and human serum	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ multiplexed detection in complex systems, such as human cancer cell extracts and serum 	[73]
	gold-coated FO-SPR	Carboxyl-SAM	MA-IFX20G2 capture antibodies	1.42 ng mL ⁻¹ 1.00 ng mL ⁻¹ 1.34 ng mL ⁻¹ <2ng mL ⁻¹	therapeutic monoclonal antibody infliximab (IFX)	serum plasma whole blood dried blood spots extracts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ multiplexed detection ▪ no matrix effects for the given dilution factor ▪ detection time 10 min 	[85]
ORGANIC	gold surface	SAMs of mercaptosuccinic acid (MSA)	antibody-CA 15-3	0.10 to 500 U mL ⁻¹ / 0.0998 U mL ⁻¹ .	Carbohydrate Antigen 15-3 (CA-15-3)	human serum	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ minimized matrix effects ▪ minimal reagent/sample amounts ▪ assay time ~30 min 	[91]
	gold surface	SAMs of 2-mercaptoethanol (ME)	thiolated miRNA-145	1.0 fM – 10 nM/ 0.56 fM	miRNA-145	human serum	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ detection in complex matrix ▪ high selectivity against single and two mismatching base pairs ▪ rapid, easy, automated, reproducible procedures 	[92]
	gold surface	poly-l-lysine-g-maleimide (26%) and an anionic oligopeptide (CEEEEE)	PNA probe side chains	0.58 pg μL ⁻¹	wild-type and KRAS p.G12D-mutated DNA	human plasma	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ antifouling properties ▪ no preanalytical treatment of the patient's plasma ▪ no need to isolate DNA from plasma ▪ no PCR amplification of the target sequence 	[100]
	gold surface	carboxybetaine methacrylamide (CBMAA) and N-(2-hydroxypropyl) methacrylamide (HPMAA) monomer units (pHPMAA-CBMAA)	antibody, amino-modified oligonucleotide probe	6 nmol L ⁻¹	miR-16	blood plasma	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ fouling resistance for the pHPMAA-CBMAA(15%) coating to blood plasma 2 orders of magnitude better than ODN-functionalized mixed OEG-SAMs 	[102]

ORGANIC	gold surface	triethylene glycol (PEG (3))-pentramer carboxybetaine	mouse monoclonal antibodies (mAB-ARG1 N-term) and mAB-ARG1 C-term) against human Arginase 1		human Arginase 1	human plasma	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ antifouling properties tested with undiluted and diluted pooled human plasma ▪ comparison with phosphorylcholine-, PEG-carboxybetaine and sulfobetaine-based layers ▪ ultralow fouling properties with a thickness of the layer (< 2 nm) compatible with sensitive SPR detection 	[31]
	gold surface	mixed SAM of 3-mercapto-1-propanol (MPO) and a further surface passivation employing a positively charged lipid bilayer mimic, 2-dioleoyl-sn-glycero-3-ethylphosphocholine (EPC+)	thiolated protein A	0.05 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for cholera toxin	IgG and cholera toxin	human serum and plasma	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ layer potentially useful for the detection of clinically relevant targets within a range of complex biological matrices (given the universal nature of protein A) 	[103]
	gold surface	cystamine and GO-COOH sheets	anti-CK19 antibody	0.001–100 pg mL^{-1} / 0.05 pg mL^{-1}	cytolerayin19 (CK19) protein	human plasma	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ antifouling properties of COOH modified GO sheets on Au film ▪ enhancement of the field energy propagation intensity ▪ higher sensitivity for the detection of CK19 protein compared to a conventional Au-based SPR chip. 	[107]
	gold surface	rGO (CVD grown graphene nanosheets transferred by wet-chemical means to gold SPR)	folic acid (FA)	5–500 fM/5fM 3 – 26 nM/2.63 nM	folic acid protein (FAP) Lysozyme	human serum and milk	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ highly anti-fouling interface <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ long life time ▪ potential to regenerate it 	[108]

BIOINTERFACE	gold film	6-mercapto-1-hexanol	aptamers 6th-62 and 6th-62-40	100 nM–10 pM/ 10 pM	CRP	human serum	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> AuNP enhanced aptamer-antibody sandwich measurements multiplexed should be investigated 	[130]
	a tilted fiber Bragg gratings inscribed into a single-mode silica FO with a ~50 nm gold film successive deposited	6-mercapto-1-hexanol	thiolated aptamers against mammaglobin-A (MAMA2)	49 cells mL ⁻¹ 10 cells mL ⁻¹ with AuNPs	mammaglobin-A	breast tumor MDA-MB-415 and control HEK293 cells	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> improved LOD using thiolated MAMA2 aptamers functionalized AuNPs selectivity tested with high concentrations of different cell lines 	[131]
	periodically corrugated gold film	poly[(N-(2-hydroxypropyl)-methacrylamide)-co-(carboxybetaine methacrylamide)] (poly(HPMA-co-CBMAA)) brushes	thrombin binding aptamer HD1	1–20 nM	thrombin	human blood plasma	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> antifouling properties label-free analysis of thrombin no need for additional steps for signal enhancement 	[132]
	FO-SPR sensor tip	alkane thiol PEG	3D DNA origami structures (LS and DE) DNA Tetrahedron for thrombin-binding aptamer (TBA)	1–248 nM LS 11.2 nM DE 6.1 nM tetrahedron 10.7 nM without PEG filling	human α -thrombin		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> better performance in the absence of PEG backfilling improved bioreceptor orientation and accessibility a wider linear range compared to previously reported thrombin biosensors 	[133]
	indium-tin-oxide (ITO) substrate	hollow Au spike-like nanoparticle (hAuSN)	DNA 3 way-Junction (3WJ) for hemagglutinin (HA) binding aptamer	0 pM –100 nM/ 1 pM	avian influenza virus	chicken serum	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> selectivity tested against other proteins (Cyt C, BSA, spike protein (S), Myo and HA protein) 	[136]

BIOINTERFACE	gold surface	capture hairpin probes (CP) and trigger SDA cycles	ODN-functionalized AuNPs	0.15 pM 0.22 pM	miR-21 miR-192	fetal bovine serum (FBS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> selectivity against single-base mismatched, double-base mismatch, non-complementary and miRNA-222 	[145]
	gold surface	initiator probe (IP), capture probe (CB), DSN-assisted target miRNA recycling and generation of intermediate single-stranded DNA	DNA sandwich assemblies through the HCR	5 pM–10 nM 2.45 pM	miR-10b	FBS and culture soup of Hs746t cells; urine and plasma samples of mice with Hs746t xenografts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> enhanced LSPR signal with gold nanotags capped with tannic acid binding to DNA sandwich structures 	[146]
	gold surface	Lomant'reagent	PNA probe and ODN functionalized AuNPs	2.5 aM	cell-free fetal DNA bearing single gene SRY	plasma from pregnant women	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> successfully applied to reveal male cell-free fetal DNA in the plasma of pregnant women at early gestational ages not required costly, time-consuming, and prone to sample contamination PCR-based procedures. 	[150]
	gold surface	Lomant'reagent	PNA probe and ODN functionalized AuNPs	~1aM	blood KRAS and NRAS mutations	plasma from colon rectal cancer patients	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> not required the extraction of tumor DNA from plasma detection in volumes as low as 40 μL of plasma 	[151]

Abbreviations: SAMs: self-assembled monolayers; PNA: peptide nucleic acid; KRAS: Kirsten rat sarcoma viral oncogene; NRAS: neuroblastoma ras viral oncogene; ODN: oligodeoxynucleotides; OEG: oligo(ethylene glycol); PEG: polyethylene glycol; Graphene Oxide; rGO: reduced Graphene Oxide; CVD: Chemical Vapour Deposition; APTES: (3-Aminopropyl)triethoxysilane; CFU: Colony Forming Units; AuNPs: gold nanoparticles; AFP: Alpha-fetoprotein; CRP: C-reactive protein; PSA: prostate-specific antigen; A.R.: aspect ratio; CA15-3: cancer antigen; CEA: carcinoembryonic antigen; FO: Fiber optic; LS: lateral

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surfaces; **DE**: distal ends; **Cyt C**: cytochrome c; **BSA**: bovine serum albumin; **Myo**: myoglobin; **S**: spike protein, **HA**: emagglutinin protein; **SDA**: strand displacement amplification; **DSN**: duplex-specific nuclease; **HCR**: hybridization chain reaction; **SRY**: Sex-determining Region Y.

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